

where $x = \frac{i_E}{i_{lim}}$, i_E = current at potential E which is valid in the entire region $0 < x < 1$. The plots of E_{a_e} vs $\log \left[\frac{x(5.5-x)}{5(1-x)} \right]$ yield the values of $\frac{0.060}{\alpha n}$ (slope) and $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (intercept). Also, for an irreversible wave the half wave potential is related to the rate constant for the electrode reduction by the expression,

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = E_0 + \frac{0.060}{\alpha n} \log \left[0.89 k_{f,h}^0 \sqrt{t/D} \right] \quad \dots (2)$$

where $k_{f,h}^0$ is the formal rate constant at a reference potential $E_0 = -0.2412$ volts vs S.C.E. and D and t have their usual significance. The reference potential in the present investigations has been chosen as the normal hydrogen electrode potential (-0.2412 volts vs S.C.E.) and the values of $D^{\frac{1}{2}}$ have been obtained using Ilkovic equation. Values of αn and $k_{f,h}^0$ have been calculated and presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS

ligand conc. (mM)	[UO ₂ ²⁺] = 1 × 10 ⁻⁴ M			
	-E _{1/2} (volts vs SCE)	αn	D ^{1/2} × 10 ³ (cm sec ⁻²)	k _{f,h} ⁰ × 10 ⁶ (cm ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)
(a) System : UO ₂ (II)-DHP, pH = 4.4				
2.0	0.460	0.750	2.33	2.71
4.0	0.480	0.742	2.19	1.54
6.0	0.488	0.740	2.03	1.16
8.0	0.492	0.739	1.95	1.01
(b) System : UO ₂ (II)-AHP, pH = 4.4				
2.0	0.455	0.752	2.41	3.19
4.0	0.476	0.749	2.34	1.52
6.0	0.485	0.752	2.16	1.20
8.0	0.490	0.747	2.17	1.10
(c) System : UO ₂ (II)-HPT, pH = 4.6				
2.0	0.463	0.747	2.18	1.74
4.0	0.481	0.741	2.11	1.46
6.0	0.490	0.740	2.03	1.10
8.0	0.493	0.740	1.86	1.02

A perusal of the results show that the $k_{f,h}^0$ values for reduction of UO₂²⁺ in presence of the same concentration of the ligands follow the order HPT < DHP < AHP. Since higher value of the rate constant signifies easier reduction and hence lower stability of the complex, the order of the strength of the metal ligand bond in the complexes of the three ligands appears to be HPT > DHP > AHP.

Uranyl ion falls in the category of hard acids (class 'a') for which the strength of the metal ligand bond should follow the O > N > S order of the donor atoms, so that the order of stability of the complexes formed with the three ligands under study should be DHP > AHP > HPT. For DHP and AHP, the studies were made under similar conditions (both in aqueous media) and the observed behaviour is as expected from theoretical considerations. Deviation in the behaviour of HPT may be because the study was made in 30% methanol medium which has a dielectric constant lower than that of water.

Vlcek⁵ also approximated that a complex with a nonhomogeneous coordination sphere will be reduced more easily (i.e., the rate constant for reduction will be higher) than one with fully homogeneous coordination sphere. Consistent with the above, the rate constant for the reduction of the AHP complex is higher than that for the reduction of the DHP complex.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-Sulphamethoxazole Complexes with Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Mg²⁺

M. S. MAYADEO and S. BHATTACHARJEE

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay-400 019

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In the present investigation, potentiometric studies have been carried out on 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphamethoxazole and its complexes with some bivalent metal ions. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphamethoxazole was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine in alcohol-DMF mixture and was repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 240° (observed). All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal salts and perchloric acid both of A. R. grade. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations². Other experimental details were the same as in our earlier communication³.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned here that the ligand does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental

conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the course of titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after two hours. This was further confirmed by taking tit of a sample titration mixture from time to time.

In the ligand, it is the phenolic OH group that takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various B values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the formation curve (B vs $\bar{n}_A$) was plotted. The pK_1^H corresponding to phenolic H was obtained by half integral method at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$. This was further corroborated by plotting the graph of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphamethoxazole.

From the titration curves, $\bar{n}$ and pL values for metal-ligand systems were also determined. Values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were determined from the curves $\bar{n}$ vs pL by half integral method and the results were corroborated by plotting the graph of $\left[\log \frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}} \right]$ vs pL . As in the cases of Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} complexes the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was found to be less than 1.78 log units, these were computed by the least square method, and the results are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

Cations	t = 25°		μ = 0.1			
	H ⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
log K ₁	8.18	7.56	6.58	4.18	3.90	2.94
log K ₂	—	6.03	5.50	—	—	2.87

* The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be $Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Mg^{2+}$. This is in agreement with that of Irving and Williams⁴.

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Electrode Kinetics of the Polarographic Reduction of Ni(II) in the Presence of Increasing Concentrations of L-4-Hydroxyproline and L-Tryptophan

J. C. KHATRI and MUKHTAR SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra-282 002

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THOUGH a few polarographic data^{1,2} on the electroreduction of Ni(II) in the presence of tryptophan are mentioned in literature, systematic and comprehensive studies on the electrode kinetics of this system are lacking. Besides, studies on the electrode kinetics of Ni(II) in the presence of L-4-hydroxyproline (LHP) have not been reported so far. The present paper aims at studying the influence of increasing concentrations of LHP and L-tryptophan on the kinetics of electrode reaction of Ni(II) under different conditions of pH.

Experimental

Solutions of $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $NaClO_4$ were prepared from reagent grade (A. R., B. D. H.) chemicals in conductivity water. L-4-Hydroxyproline (LHP) was a Fluka (Puriss, CHR) product, and L-tryptophan was a Reanal (Hungary) A. R. product and their aqueous solutions were used. The concentration of the depolarizer was kept at $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ in each case and that of supporting electrolyte ($NaClO_4$) at 0.1 M. Requisite amount of Triton X-100 was added to suppress the maximum.